

What The Conventions of Grammars Tell Us About Communicative Efficiency: Some Current Issues and Prospects

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Section 1: Introduction

Many early proposals for communicative efficiency were first formulated by linguists working in “language typology”, on the basis of patterns in the grammars of the world’s languages. This inference from grammars to hypothesized preferences in performance was often tested on small samples of manually collected usage data, sometimes decades before psycholinguists and computational linguists began testing their ideas about ease of processing and efficiency using experiments and larger databases, and in languages going beyond English, German and Standard European.

Greenberg (1966) proposed morphological hierarchies such as Singular > Plural > Dual > Paucal for number marking on nouns, and Nominative > Accusative > Dative > Other for case marking, based on the cross-linguistic distribution of these morphemes and on patterns of allomorphy (with declining allomorphy down the hierarchies, more zero expression at the top end and increasing phonological complexity in lower positions). In order to explain these patterns in grammars he pointed to correlations with (declining) frequencies of usage within languages (e.g. Singular nouns in a corpus of Sanskrit = 70.3%, Plural = 25.1%, Dual = 4.6%). These performance-grammar correspondences led to an efficiency principle of **Minimize Forms** in Hawkins (2004, 2014) and to similar formulations with even more extensive cross-linguistic performance-grammar support in Haspelmath (2021).

Greenberg’s (1963) word order universals and his proposed correlations between head orderings in grammars (VO languages prefer Prepositions before NP, OV languages prefer Postpositions after NP, etc, cf. Dryer 1992) led to a processing efficiency explanation in Hawkins (1990), before performance data were actually collected from a range of typologically different languages in Hawkins (1994) that corroborated the central idea derived from grammars: **Minimize Domains** (Hawkins 2004, 2014). This same idea has now been supported in large cross-linguistic electronic databases and captured using a Dependency Grammar Framework in **Dependency Length Minimization** (Futrell et al. 2015, Futrell et al. 2020).

I.e. it has long been recognized in language typology that considerations of processing ease and efficiency have had a profound impact on grammars and on their evolution and are visible in the typological variation we see today. I refer to this as the Performance-Grammar Correspondence Hypothesis in Hawkins (2004, 2014):

Performance-Grammar Correspondence Hypothesis (PGCH)

Grammars have conventionalized syntactic structures in proportion to their degree of preference in performance, as evidenced by patterns of selection in corpora and by ease of processing in psycholinguistic experiments.

It is because of the PGCH that a comparison of many grammars can reveal the efficiencies and performance preferences that led to their conventionalization and suggest principles for actual testing on corpus data and in experiments on different languages.

Some further examples of observed performance-grammar correspondences

- Keenan-Comrie (1977) Accessibility Hierarchy (SU>DO>IO/OBL>GEN): grammatical cut-off points across languages match declining ease of processing in English and other languages (Keenan & S. Hawkins 1987, cf. Hawkins 1999, Lau & Tanaka 2021);
- filler-gap hierarchies for increasingly complex clause-embedding environments: again cut-off points across grammars correspond to declining processing ease in languages with numerous gap-containing environments (including subjacency-violating languages like Akan, Saah & Goodluck 1995, Hawkins 1999);
- reverse hierarchies across languages for gaps in simpler relativization domains and resumptive pronouns in more complex domains match the performance distribution of gaps to pronouns within languages such as Hebrew and Cantonese in which both are grammatical (in some syntactic positions), gaps being preferred in the simpler, pronouns in the more complex relatives (Hawkins 2004, Matthews & Yip 2003, Ariel 1999);
- parallel function effects facilitate relative clause processing and acquisition and they also extend relativization possibilities beyond normal constraints holding in languages such as Basque and Hebrew (Sheldon 1974, MacWhinney 1982, Clancy et al. 1986, Hawkins 2004, Aldai 2003, Cole 1976);
- declining acceptability of increasingly complex center embeddings, in languages in which these are grammatical, is matched by hierarchies of permitted center embeddings across grammars, with cut-offs down these hierarchies (Hawkins 1994)
- (nominative) subject before (accusative) object ordering is massively preferred in the performance of languages in which both SO & OS are grammatical [Japanese, Korean, Finnish, German] and is also massively preferred as a basic order or as the only order across grammars (Hawkins 1994, Gibson 1998, Tomlin 1986, Primus 1999, see (4D));
- performance preferences for subjects that obey the Person Hierarchy (1st,2nd > 3rd) in English (whereby the bus hit me is preferably passivized to I was hit by the bus) have been conventionalized into a grammatical/ungrammatical distinction in languages such as Lummi (Bresnan et al. 2001) - more generally "hard constraints" (in e.g. Lummi) are claimed to correlate with "soft" constraints (in e.g. English);
- the distinction between zero agreement with adjacent modifiers of head nouns versus explicit agreement non-locally in the grammar of Warlpiri matches the environments in which zero and explicit agreement forms are preferred in performance in languages with choices (Hawkins 2004).

So what do the grammars of the world's languages tell us today that is of relevance for the current state of the art in language processing and specifically in theories of communicative efficiency? I examine one very general set of patterns that have not received the attention they deserve and that suggest a principle of efficiency rather different from that which lies at the heart of several current theories. At issue is the role and significance of online prediction in efficient processing.

Section 2: Left-Right Asymmetries

There are numerous patterns of left-right asymmetry in grammatical universals that compete with the more symmetrical patterns of Greenberg's VO vs OV universals. In these asymmetries grammars systematically place some words and phrases before others. Since processing takes place sequentially, word by word, speakers and listeners are regularly processing some items before others, therefore, regardless of their other grammatical features and language type. *Prima facie* (and by the PGCH) there has got to be a good processing reason for this. I will argue that the grammatical details of these cross-linguistic patterns reveal very clearly what makes them efficient and what their advantages are for online processing.

We see asymmetrical ordering most consistently whenever one linguistic category is asymmetrically dependent on another, e.g.

- (1) a gap on a moved WH filler:
Who_i did you go to the movies with O_i?
- (2) a reflexive anaphor on its antecedent:
Mary_i was very pleased with herself_i.
- (3) a narrow-scope quantifier on a wide-scope one:
Everyone was reading a linguistics book
- (4) a predication on its topic:
As for John, things are not going well

In such cases the dependent category B generally or sometimes invariably stands to the right of the independent category A and is processed after it, i.e. A+B.

Hawkins (2002/2004) proposed a principle of processing that could be derived from these asymmetries in grammars: **Maximize Online Processing**. It is always the more completely and correctly and more immediately processable category, A, that precedes the dependent one, B, in these cases, while B is positioned later where it too can be immediately and completely and correctly interpreted at the time of its processing, but only by referring back to A on which it is dependent for some at least of its property assignments. If the ordering is reversed, B+A, the processing of the dependent B would be systematically delayed and incomplete and possibly incorrect at the time it is encountered (with so-called "unassignments" of properties online and possibly "misassignments").

Section 3: Maximize Online Processing (MaOP) (Hawkins 2002/2004)

(5) **Maximize On-line Processing (MaOP)**

The human processor prefers to maximize the set of properties that are assignable to each item X as X is processed, thereby increasing O(n-line) P(roperly) to U(ltimate) P(roperly) ratios. The maximization difference between competing orders and

structures will be a function of the number of properties that are unassigned or misassigned to X in a structure/sequence S, compared with the number in an alternative.

Unassignment factors = the number of words and phrases that undergo some temporary unassignment of properties online; the number of any mother-daughter attachments temporarily unassignable; the number of relations of combination or dependency temporarily unassignable.

E.g. antecedents preferred before reflexive anaphors:

(6) *John_i washed himself_i or Washed John_i himself_i*

better than e.g.

(7) *Washed himself_i John_i*

because in (6) the antecedent *John* occurs first and is fully processable as is, and the anaphor *himself* can then immediately receive its co-index and its semantic coreference when it is encountered by looking back to *John_i*. In the reverse order (7) the anaphor occurs first and its complete processing is delayed until *John_i* occurs, whereupon a co-index and semantic coreference can be assigned retrospectively to *himself_i* at *John_i*.

Hence 2 less properties are assignable immediately to word B as it is encountered in B+A, and 2 more to A, compared with the sequence A+B in which all of A's properties are assigned at A, and all of B's properties are assigned at B as well. Simplifying, let us imagine that there are 10 grammatical and lexical properties to be assigned in each of these sentences, then if the Online Property to Ultimate Property ratios in A + B are as in (8):

(8)	Word 1	Word 2 = A	Word 3 = B	
Properties Assigned:	2	4	4	
OP-to-UP Ratio:	2/10	6/10	10/10	
	20%	60%	100%	= 180 total

then the ratios with the reverse B+A would be lower, as shown in (9), because fewer properties are assignable to B online as a result of its incomplete and delayed processing, and these missing properties would then need to be assigned at A and distributed retrospectively to B:

(9)	Word 1	Word 2 = B	Word 3 = A	
Properties Assigned:	2	2	6	
OP-to-UP Ratio:	2/10	4/10	10/10	
	20%	40%	100%	= 160 total

Misassignments = those properties that are both unassigned online and simultaneously a wrong property e.g. a mother-daughter attachment or relation of combination or dependency is misassigned that needs to be corrected subsequently, i.e. a garden path. Predictions for the severity of these can be made by the grammatical criteria in Hawkins (2004: 51-61). E.g. *The horse raced past the barn fell* involves far worse unassignments and misassignments compared to *The horse that was raced past the barn fell*, than *I believe John is a fool* does compared to *I believe that John is a fool*.

I.e. complete processability of an item as soon as it is encountered in online parsing and production is preferred over partial processing (with unassignments) or erroneous processing (with misassignments), requiring backtracking, reconstruction of the tree, etc.

Section 4: Some Left-Right Asymmetries

(4A) WH-first before its Gap

(10a) *What_i did you see a boy stealing 0_i in the grocery store last night?*

(10b) **You saw a boy stealing 0_i in the grocery store last night what_i?*

There are some 29% of languages in WALS (Dryer 2005) that have a WH-fronting rule as in English (10a) (212/730), the remainder having WH in situ, or some attachment or adjacency to V especially in SOV languages. This movement to the left, as opposed to the right (10b), creating a “filler before gap” or “filler before subcategorizer” structure (Hawkins 2014: 172-176), is almost exceptionless. Polinsky (2002) cites only American Sign Language and Tibeto-Burman Meithei as possible WH-last languages of which she is aware, i.e. just 2 vs the 212 with WH-first.

There are numerous processing considerations that have long been known to make gap-filling difficult (J.D. Fodor 1978, 1984, 1989, Frazier et al. 1983). The cross-linguistic asymmetry in WH+Gap vs Gap+WH ordering is striking. I attribute it, in large part at least, to **Maximize Online Processing**. In (10a) the filler can be processed at the first word, and a gap is then postulated as soon as it can be (by the Active Filler Hypothesis of Clifton & Frazier 1989), in a way compatible with the co-occurrence requirements of the grammar and lexicon, here right after *stealing* as the direct object of this latter. Both WH and the gap are processed as soon as they are encountered. In (10b) where the gap precedes the filler, there is no filler to activate the gap, and the gap will be regularly unassigned, and possibly even misassigned online. Similarly, in “direct association theories” linking fillers to their subcategorizers there is a similar delay in assigning *what_i* to *stealing_i* in (10b) as there is in assigning *what_i* to the gap that it has retrospectively assigned to the immediate right of *stealing*.

(4B) Head Noun before Relative Clause

(11) *the book_i that the professor wrote 0_i*

Almost all languages with VO or head-initial syntax have NRel, i.e. N+Gap (Dryer 1992). For OV languages Hawkins (2014:148) shows, using data from WALS (Dryer 2005, Dryer with Gensler 2005) that RelN is found only in rigid SOV languages like Japanese, and not in non-rigid ones like Persian:

(12)	WALS	Rel+N	N+Rel/Mixed/Correlative/Other
	Rigid SOV	50% (17)	50% (17)
	Non-rigid SOV	0%	100% (17)

Since roughly half the world's languages are VO with almost all having NRel and since two thirds of OV languages also have NRel (i.e. 5/6 or 83% have NRel) there is a clear asymmetrical preference for N+Gap across languages, just as there is for WH+Gap, although this preference competes now with Cross-Category Harmony (Hawkins 1983) and ultimately Minimize Domains (Hawkins 2004): the more head-final phrases there are in a language to contain an NP consisting of Noun and Relative, the more it will favor noun finality and resist an independent preference for N+Rel.

Why is Rel+N and Gap+N dispreferred? In the Gap+N structure the gap will be regularly unassigned prior to encountering the head, just as it was unassigned prior to WH in (10b). In the English (11) the filler head noun precedes the gap and can be processed as is and the later gap can then be immediately activated and processed by the Active Filler Hypothesis once a relative clause structure has been activated. But in the reverse Gap+N there will again be unassignments and delays in processing, and possibly misassignments, and these have indeed been shown to occur in languages like Japanese and Korean. Clancy et al. (1986) conducted experiments on structures like (13) in Japanese:

- (13) *Zoo-ga* [[*0_i* *kirin-o* *taoshi-ta*] *shika-oi*] *nade-ta*
 elephant-NOM Gap giraffe-ACC knocked down deer-ACC patted
 'The elephant patted the deer that knocked down the giraffe.'

Zoo-ga was regularly first misrecognized as the nominative subject of *taoshi-ta* within a simple main clause analysis of *Zoo-ga kirin-o taoshi-ta* (with the meaning 'the elephant knocked down the giraffe') and then the words and phrases were reanalyzed in accordance with the Rel+N structure shown in brackets. The on-line misassignments are quite severe in this example, by the criteria in Hawkins (2004:51-61,205-210). In the event that the first two NPs encountered in the online parse do not match the co-occurrence requirements of the first verb, *taoshi-ta*, then the phrases and relations involving misassignments in (13) will be temporarily unassigned. Either way unassignments and/or misassignments are extensive for RelN.

(4C) Antecedent before Reflexive Anaphor

This asymmetry and its motivation in terms of **Maximize Online Processing** was exemplified for (6) and (7) above. Empirically the distribution of antecedents and anaphors is highly correlated with the asymmetric preference for Subjects before Objects across languages (see (4D) below), since Antecedent and Anaphor are typically Subject and Object respectively and the object is asymmetrically dependent on the subject syntactically and semantically, c-commanded by it (Reinhart 1976), etc. Hence this asymmetrical ordering is motivated both by general Subject before Object considerations and by the co-indexing and coreference property assignments mentioned above.

The quantities of languages exemplifying Antecedent before Reflexive Anaphor will be at least those for Subject before Object, therefore, (see (4D)) and exceptions should generally be limited to languages like Malagasy with a strong basic VOS word order (Keenan 1976a):

- (14) *Manaja tena_i Rabe_i*
 respect self Rabe
 ‘Rabe respects himself.’

(4D) Subjects before Objects

According to Tomlin some 96% of his 402 language sample order Subject before Object:

- | | | | | | | |
|----------------|---|----------|---|----------|---|---------|
| (15) SOV (168) | > | VSO (37) | > | VOS (12) | > | OVS (5) |
| SVO (180) | | | | | | OSV (0) |
| 87% | | 9% | | 3% | | 1% |

This asymmetry becomes even more compelling when basic grammatical relations are broken down, more precisely, into their component properties of morphological marking, syntactic configuration, and semantics (theta-roles). Primus (1999) proposes the following hierarchies in which lower positions are asymmetrically dependent on each higher position:

- (16) Case Morphology: Nominative > Accusative > Dative > Other
 Absolutive > Ergative > Dative > Other
- (17) Syntax: higher structural position (c-commanding) > lower position (c-commanded)
- (18) Semantics (theta-roles): Agent > Recipient > Patient
 Experiencer > Stimulus

Each of these hierarchies is then preferably linearized with higher positions to the left of each lower position, with particularly strong linear asymmetries resulting when multiple hierarchies reinforce one another in a given language type, and with greater variation when hierarchies conflict. So a significant number of languages that have been (mis)classified as OS are those with ergative-absolutive case morphology, and these often position the Absolutive first, in accordance with the Case hierarchy (16). The preference for SO is accordingly stronger in nominative-accusative languages in which all higher hierarchy positions can align, Nominative, C-commanding configuration and Agent, than in ergative languages in which Absolutive is the highest case position in (16). This is shown in the figures from Hawkins (2022) taken from WALS (Comrie 2013):

- | | | |
|--|-----------------|-------|
| (19) S _{Nom} + O _{Acc} | 44/50 languages | (88%) |
| O _{Acc} + S _{Nom} | 2/50 | (4%) |
| No dominant order | 4/50 | (8%) |
| (20) S _{Erg} + O _{Abs} | 18/27 languages | (67%) |
| O _{Abs} + S _{Erg} | 2/27 | (7%) |
| No dominant order | 7/27 | (26%) |

The asymmetric dependencies in (16)-(18) may be semantic (you can't have a Patient without an Agent, (cf. Jackendoff 1972, Dowty 1991), or morphological (an Accusative requires a

Nominative, an Ergative requires an Absolutive), or syntactic (a lower c-commanded position in the tree requires a higher c-commanding one).

In all cases the preferred linearization positions the A category first and the dependent B later. In this way precise details of B's interpretation and syntax can be assigned immediately by reference to a prior A, and without unassignments or misassignments in accordance with **Maximize Online Processing**. There will be no attempt to assign a c-commanded object into a tree structure that has not yet been constructed online with a higher c-commanding subject, the theta-role of the second argument can be more precisely and immediately determined by reference to the first. The asymmetry in dependency is least strong for the morphological hierarchies (16) when these are clearly differentiated by explicit markers regardless of their ordering and this may explain why the linearization preferences of the syntactic (17) and semantic hierarchies (18) are stronger and generally override the case hierarchy resulting in what is still a strong 67% preference for Ergative first in (20), even though Absolutive is higher in (16).

The preference for subjects before objects is then further reinforced by the many additional properties and dependencies that correlate with subject and object in transitive clauses, and which provide additional online processing motivations for the A+B ordering thru **Maximize Online Processing**. Keenan (1976b) mentions Independent Existence (the subject does not depend on a transitive verb for its reference), Autonomous Reference (the subject does not depend on other NPs in the clause, i.e. no **Heself loves John*), High Referentiality (the subject attracts highly referential NPs, like definite NPs only in Malagasy, Tagalog, and Bantu languages), Wide Scope (subjects have wider scope, see (4I) below), Topicality (subjects are regularly topics, see (4E)). In all these cases the transitive subject can be fully and immediately processed at the outset, and the dependent object can be fully and immediately processed too by referring back to the subject, but unassignments and misassignments would result in the reversed order.

(4E) Topic before Comment

In languages with clear topic positions, especially those that have explicit topic marking, “sentence-external topics” and are topic-prominent like Chinese (Li & Thompson 1981) there is a strong preference for topic to precede comment. This can sometimes be reversed into Comment before Topic, and there are numerous grammatical and pragmatic intricacies that are relevant here, as shown by Lambrecht (1994), Polinsky (2002), and others. There are also correlations between topic status and givenness, definiteness and genericness. This is illustrated for Japanese in (21) (Kuno 1973: 59), in which an indefinite topic is ungrammatical and must instead be either definite or generic:

- (21) **Oozei no hito wa party ni kimasita*
 Many people TOP party to came, i.e. Many people came to the party.

There is no purely pragmatic and information structure explanation for why topics can be generic, but not indefinite, and for the preferred ordering. Instead it is argued in Hawkins (2004) and Primus (1999) that there are numerous asymmetrical dependencies between them and it is generally the Comment that depends on the Topic. Gundel (1988:210) states that the Comment predication is “assessed relative to the topic” of the sentence, Reinhart (1982) talks of its “aboutness”. Hawkins (2004:235-238) gives numerous examples from Mandarin Chinese taken from Tsao (1978) showing that the Comment depends asymmetrically on the Topic for argument and predicate enrichments in examples such as (22)-(24) given in their literal translations:

- (22) This man (Topic Particle), mind simple. I.e. this man’s mind is simple.
- (23) His three children (Topic particle), one serves as lawyer.
- (24) Fish (Topic particle), tuna is now the most expensive. I.e. tuna is now the most expensive thing relative to fish.

If the Comment occurred first and the Topic last, these enrichment properties would be regularly unassigned and there would be misassignments as well. Meanwhile the Topic itself is fully processable in initial position, but only if definite and mutually identifiable by speaker and hearer and cognitively accessible (cf. Levelt 1989:260), or else generic when the speaker refers to all potential referents of a noun, as opposed to some unspecified and undetermined subset.

One particularly strong cross-linguistic tendency, noted first by Gundel (1988) and by Lambrecht (1994) and Polinsky (2002), is the preference for topics that mark a new topic or that signal a topic shift to require or prefer initial position. This makes sense by Maximize Online Processing. If there is a new Topic, and that Topic follows the Comment, then the dependencies inherent in the Comment will be regularly unassignable to it at the time the Comment is processed, and can be readily misassigned to a previous Topic.

(4F) Wide Scope before Narrow Scope Quantifiers & Operators

- (3) *Everyone was reading a linguistics book.*

The wide scope-narrow scope difference here is correlated with the asymmetric subject-object dependency and Passivization to *A linguistics book was read by everyone* is preferred in the event that the scope is to be reversed. More generally, the correlation across languages between semantic scope and linear ordering appears to be strong, with some languages (English) permitting more variability and others (e.g. Hungarian, Kiss 2002) less. The preference for scope mirroring the order of presentation is predicted by Maximize Online Processing since there would be frequent unassignments or misassignments to the narrow scope element if and when it was presented first.

(4G) Complementizers before Subordinate Clause

The distribution of free-standing complementizers before or after a subordinate S has a very similar distribution to that of head noun and relative clause (Hawkins 2014:153-55, cf. Dryer 2009) and can be similarly explained by the interaction of Minimize Domains and Maximize Online Processing.

(25) VO languages	Comp + S	74% (140)
	S + Comp	0% (0)
OV languages	Comp + S	12% (22)
	S + Comp	14% (27)

(4H) Restrictive precedes Appositive modifiers of N

- (26) a. Students that major in mathematics, who must work very hard (R+A)
 b. *Students, who must work very hard, that major in mathematics (A+R)
- If (26b) were grammatical there would be regular semantic misassignments online with the appositive claim being predicated first of all students, rather than of the restricted subset.

Section 5: Some Alternative Processing Ideas for Asymmetries

(5A) Working Memory Reduction (Gibson 1998)

“OVS ... orders are more complex at the initial nouns because it is necessary to retain the prediction of a subject noun at this location. ... SVO sentences are expected to be more frequent than OVS ..., because they require less memory to produce and comprehend.”

I.e. avoid structures like OVS in which a category B, a direct object, predicts another A, a subject., and precedes it. More generally, online prediction is bad for working memory since it increases processing load.

NB! Ergative subjects are a counterexample to this since they predict an absolutive object and still generally precede it (recall (20)), albeit less frequently than nominative subjects (in (19)).

(5B) Surprisal Theory (Levy 2008)

“... the results from psycholinguistics indicat[e] that the bulk of language processing load comes from the degree to which linguistic elements such as words are unexpected in context. Surprisal theory ... formalizes this idea and claims that all processing difficulty results from the extent to which elements are unexpected in context ...” (quote from Futrell, Levy & Gibson 2020)

I.e. the less expected and predicted a word is, the larger its surprisal and the greater the processing load, while the more predicted it is, the less its surprisal, and the less processing load. More generally, online prediction is good.

Hence, if one category systematically predicts another in these left-right asymmetries, then placing the predicting one first should reduce the surprisal and processing load for the second and should be preferred. But this contradicts Gibson (1998): objects should now precede subjects since the subject in the OVS order is predicted and expected in context!

This would work well for the ergative subjects of (20), but not the nominative subjects of (19).

(5C) Uniform Information Density (Jaeger 2010)

“Within the bounds defined by grammar, speakers prefer utterances that distribute information uniformly across the signal (information density). Where speakers have a choice between several variants to encode their message, they prefer the variant with more uniform information density”

This theory, like Gibson’s, predicts that object-first languages should be dispreferred (cf. Maurits et al. 2010 for explicit testing of this), but the reasoning is different. The predictiveness of the direct object results in an uneven spike in information at the beginning of the clause, which makes it non-uniform compared with other orders, especially SVO and VSO.

Again, ergative subjects in (20) go counter to this. Plus, SOV is counterfactually predicted to be a dispreferred order in the Maurits et al. study! In the most recent WALS data (Dryer 2013) it is the most common single type (SOV=48%, SVO=42%, VSO&VOS=10%)

More generally, left-right asymmetries of A+B with A predicting B would be bad according to this theory, when they front-load information density and distort the uniformity of information processing throughout the string.

(5D) There is No Consistent Relation Between Online Prediction and Asymmetric Ordering

All three theories assume that online prediction is **a**, or **the**, major force in reducing processing load and in favoring certain sequences of words, whether it be the predicting before the predicted (Levy) or predicted before predicting (Gibson, Jaeger). But left-right asymmetries of A+B are not explainable by online prediction in either of these variants.

Sometimes A predicts certain aspects of B and not vice versa, sometimes B predicts A and not vice versa, sometimes neither is predictive:

(27) A predicts (certain aspects of) B and not vice versa

WH predicts there will be a gap in (4A), but not necessarily where (Fodor 1984), cf. the Active Filler Hypothesis of Clifton & Frazier (1989)

Ergative subjects predict an absolute object in (4D)

Topics (if clearly topic-marked) predict some upcoming Comment in (4E)

A complementizer predicts a subordinate clause in (4G)

(28) B predicts (certain aspects of) A and not vice versa

Reflexive anaphor predicts there will be an Antecedent in (4C)

Accusative objects predict a nominative subject in (4D)

(29) Neither A nor B predicts the other

A noun does not predict that it is going to be modified by a relative clause and contain a gap, nor is a gap recognizable in advance of a head noun, cf. (4B)

A wide scope quantifier does not predict a narrow scope one, nor is a narrow scope quantifier recognizable as such and predictive in advance of a wide scope one, (4F)

A restrictive relative does not predict an appositive one, nor the latter the former in (4H)

Section 6: Conclusions

Asymmetries in cross-linguistic grammatical conventions point systematically to an efficiency principle whereby each item is processed as completely and as correctly as it can be and as soon as it is encountered. This is why certain categories are ordered A+B quite consistently, namely those in which B is asymmetrically dependent on A. Reversing them to B+A would make the processing of B incomplete and possibly erroneous prior to A and would delay overall processing and make it slower and more complex.

It is this Maximize Online Processing principle that is supported by left-right asymmetries, not the other theories in (5A-C). The preferred A+B may or may not reduce Working Memory Load, it may or may not reduce Surprisal/Unpredictiveness, and it may or may not make Information Density more Uniform. Likewise the dispreferred B+A may or may not conform to these theories. All three assume a major role for online prediction in processing, yet this results in contradictory preferences and appears to be irrelevant for left-right asymmetries. I.e. online prediction is not the all-important factor in language processing that current theories assume it to be, as revealed by these grammatical data in which the world's languages are systematically placing certain items A before others B. Much more important are: speed; completeness (avoid look-ahead); and correctness (avoid garden paths).

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